

Sintering and crystallization of fluoride-containing bioactive glass F3

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Supplementary material

Powder compact densification and characteristic temperatures

Table S1 Glass powder particle size fraction, psf, properties as, green body density ρ_{SO} , sinter body density ρ_{SE} , temperature of sintering onset T_{SO} , sintering offset T_{SE} , crystallization onset T_{O-1} , crystallization peak temperatures T_{P-1} and T_{P-2} , melting peaks T_{M-1} and T_{M-2} (temperature accuracy ± 5 K). $\Delta\rho = FD - GD$, $\Delta T = T_{O-1} - T_{SE}$.

Psf (μm)	GD (%)	FD (%)	$\Delta\rho$ (%)	T_{SO} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{SE} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{O-1} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{P-1} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{P-2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{M-1} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	T_{M-2} ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	ΔT (K)
bulk	-	-	-	-	-	836	857	907	-	1230	-
300-315	66 \pm 1	91 \pm 1	25 \pm 2	596 \pm 6	778 \pm 3	745	758	866	1160	1239	-33 \pm 8
200-250	65 \pm 2	95 \pm 3	30 \pm 5	592 \pm 7	751 \pm 5	734	769	868	1176	1222	-17 \pm 10
180-200	65 \pm 1	93 \pm 2	28 \pm 3	598 \pm 6	759 \pm 7	735	777	844	1185	1237	-24 \pm 13
140-180	65 \pm 1	93 \pm 2	28 \pm 3	596 \pm 1	753 \pm 5	741	765	851	1131	1265	-12 \pm 10
125-140	61 \pm 1	91 \pm 2	30 \pm 3	596 \pm 3	757 \pm 2	739	750	846	1175	1254	-18 \pm 7
100-125	60 \pm 2	94 \pm 2	34 \pm 4	592 \pm 3	745 \pm 4	725	753	840	1157	1241	-20 \pm 9
80-90	58 \pm 1	93 \pm 1	35 \pm 2	597 \pm 4	735 \pm 4	721	755	837	1177	1224	-14 \pm 9
63-80	58 \pm 1	92 \pm 1	34 \pm 2	596 \pm 1	718 \pm 2	729	749	837	1186	1249	11 \pm 7
56-63	59 \pm 1	96 \pm 1	37 \pm 2	598 \pm 2	730 \pm 1	734	755	835	1188	1241	4 \pm 6
40-45	55 \pm 1	94 \pm 1	39 \pm 2	588 \pm 2	718 \pm 6	723	746	820	1149	1214	5 \pm 11
32-40	55 \pm 2	93 \pm 1	38 \pm 3	595 \pm 1	698 \pm 1	715	728	809	1141	1172	17 \pm 6
<32	57 \pm 1	95 \pm 1	38 \pm 3	591 \pm 2	688 \pm 3	719	733	806	1189	1229	31 \pm 8

Figure S1 Relative density of sintering powder compacts, ρ_{rel} , calculated from the sample mass and sample silhouette area shrinkage, s_A , shown in Figure 1 B. GD: initial relative compact density, T_{so} sinter onset temperature, T_{SE} final densification temperature, FD: final compact density.

ATR-FTIR spectroscopy

Figure S2 shows ATR-FTIR spectra of the annealed powder compacts made from the psf 80-90 μm presented in Figure 3.

At 630 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, three broad bands are present at about 1000-1030 cm^{-1} (β), 900-930 cm^{-1} (δ) and 860 cm^{-1} (ϵ). The three bands present in the glass, assigned to the asymmetric stretching of bridging oxygen (BO) in Si–O–Si groups (β), to Si–O tetrahedra with one non-bridging oxygen (NBO) (δ) and to Si–O tetrahedra with two NBOs (ϵ) [1], do not significantly change up to 738 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ where significant amounts of crystalline phases are detectable (Figure 5 and Figure 10). Above 779 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the bands start becoming more distinct and sharper, as expected for an increased structural order. The δ band thus splits into two peaks, one at $\approx 935 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (δ_1) and another one at $\approx 900 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ (δ_2). This splitting hints on the bonding of NBO to two different network modifiers such as sodium and calcium. Such effect would well correlate with the crystallization of combeite [2], [3] as both combeite modifications ($\text{Na}_4\text{Ca}_4[\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}]$, $\text{Na}_6\text{Ca}_3[\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}]$, although both isostructural formed of six-membered $[\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}]^{12-}$ rings, differ in the occupation of the octahedral cation sites by sodium and calcium [4]. Above 813 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, close to the DTA peak temperature of the psf 80-90 μm (Figure 2), a new weak band gradually appears at about 1065 cm^{-1} (α). This band can be assigned to an overlap of asymmetric stretching vibrations of BO in higher polymerized Si–O–Si structures [5], [6] and stretching vibration of P–O [7], [3]. The authors of references [8] and [9] associate this vibration band of P–O with a surface calcium-phosphate. This weak band could therefore be related to $\text{Ca}_{14.92}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.35}(\text{SiO}_4)_{5.65}$ and cuspidine, which appears at 813 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in Figure 5. $\text{Ca}_{14.92}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.35}(\text{SiO}_4)_{5.65}$ incorporates the phosphate groups, which are supposed to exist as orthophosphate in the glass [10] into its crystalline lattice. In addition, cuspidine forms a three-dimensional network of calcium polyhedra connecting Si_2O_7 groups. The Si–O bonds, however, are elongated along the x-axis and appear longer than NBO bonds [11] which matches well with the observed new bands. Between 835 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 949 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the ϵ band shows a slightly increased intensity. This could be assigned to cuspidine as well, for which a band at 850 cm^{-1} is a good indicator [12]. Above 949 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, a further band at about 949 cm^{-1} appears (γ) whereas the ϵ band decreases. The γ band is attributed to asymmetric stretching vibrations of NBOs but in between the Si–O tetrahedral units with one or two NBOs. These units likely occur

in the wollastonite chain silicates. This interpretation is consistent with Figure 5 where significant growth of wollastonite and the decomposition of combeite and cuspidine is shown for this temperature range.

Figure S2 ATR-FTIR spectra of particle size fraction 80-90 μm heated at 10 K/min to different temperatures.

Activation energy for crystal growth

By fitting the crystal growth rate $U_L(T)$ by the usage of an Arrhenius plot (Eq. 1) in Figure 8, the activation energy for crystal growth, E_A , is received as parameter. For the present case, E_A was calculated to be 185 ± 23 kJ/mol (Figure 8 A). The main crystallizing phase in the temperature region of the major DTA peak (see Figure 2 and Figure 10) is combeite ($\text{Na}_4\text{Ca}_4[\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}]$, \blacktriangle) with minor contribution of α' - Ca_2SiO_4 (\blacklozenge) and $\text{Ca}_{14.92}(\text{PO}_4)_{2.35}(\text{SiO}_4)_{5.65}$ (\blacklozenge).

The literature offers several values of E_A for combeite crystallization in Bioglass[®] 45S5 for comparison [13]. Depending on the applied model, E_A ranges between 350 kJ/mol [14] and 192 kJ/mol [15] for thermal determination on particles smaller than 5 μm and between 350 kJ/mol [16] and 230 kJ/mol [17] for particles of 300-500 μm in size. Due to the immobility and high ionic single bond strengths of Si–O (443 kJ/mol [18]), the breaking of Si–O bonds for crystallization is not reasonable. Thus, the crystallization more likely involves the breaking of Ca–O and Na–O bonds, as the respective bond strengths are 111 and 84 kJ/mol [19], [18]. Assuming a homogeneous glass and the composition detailed in Table 1, six SiO_4 -tetrahedra should statistically be neighbored by about five calcium and two sodium atoms. Thus, for the crystallization of $\text{Na}_4\text{Ca}_4[\text{Si}_6\text{O}_{18}]$ only one calcium must be replaced by two sodium atoms. Considering the upstream crystallization of α' - Ca_2SiO_4 , seven SiO_4 -tetrahedra possess statistically about six calcium and two sodium atoms in their vicinity. Thus, for the formation of both phases, only two sodium atoms must migrate or two Na–O bonds must be broken which causes an E_A of about 168 kJ/mol which is surprisingly close to the calculated value of 192 kJ/mol and suggest a good correlation. Anyhow, considering the complex processes during crystallization including e.g. diffusion and viscous flow phenomena, the reduction and explanation only focused on the breaking of bonds is far too simplified to do justice to these.

1. References Supplementarily

- [1] Serra, J., et al., *FTIR and XPS studies of bioactive silica based glasses*. Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids, 2003. **332**(1): p. 20-27 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnoncrysol.2003.09.013>.
- [2] Gomez-Vega, J.M., et al., *Bioactive glass coatings with hydroxyapatite and Bioglass® particles on Ti-based implants. 1. Processing*. Biomaterials, 2000. **21**(2): p. 105-111 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612\(99\)00131-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-9612(99)00131-3).
- [3] Chatzistavrou, X., et al., *Influence of particle size on the crystallization process and the bioactive behavior of a bioactive glass system*. Journal of Thermal Analysis and Calorimetry, 2006. **85**(2): p. 253-259 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10973-005-7165-y>.
- [4] Ohsato, H., Y. Takeuchi, and I. Maki, *Structure of Na₄Ca₄[Si₆O₁₈]*. Acta Crystallographica Section C, 1986. **42**(8): p. 934-937 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1107/S0108270186093940>.
- [5] Cerruti, M., D. Greenspan, and K. Powers, *Effect of pH and ionic strength on the reactivity of Bioglass 45S5*. Biomaterials, 2005. **26**(14): p. 1665-74 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biomaterials.2004.07.009>.
- [6] Balamurugan, A., et al., *Synthesis and characterisation of sol gel derived bioactive glass for biomedical applications*. Materials Letters, 2006. **60**(29-30): p. 3752-3757 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.matlet.2006.03.102>.
- [7] Stoch, A., et al., *FTIR monitoring of the growth of the carbonate containing apatite layers from simulated and natural body fluids*. Journal of Molecular Structure, 1999. **511-512**: p. 287-294 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2860\(99\)00170-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2860(99)00170-2).
- [8] Filho, O.P., G.P. La Torre, and L.L. Hench, *Effect of crystallization on apatite-layer formation of bioactive glass 45S5*. Journal of Biomedical Materials Research, 1996. **30**(4): p. 509-514 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(sici\)1097-4636\(199604\)30:4<509::aid-jbm9>3.0.co;2-t](https://doi.org/10.1002/(sici)1097-4636(199604)30:4<509::aid-jbm9>3.0.co;2-t).
- [9] Pirayesh, H. and J.A. Nychka, *Sol-Gel Synthesis of Bioactive Glass-Ceramic 45S5 and its in vitro Dissolution and Mineralization Behavior*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2013. **96**(5): p. 1643-1650 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jace.12190>.
- [10] Brauer, D.S., *Bioactive Glasses—Structure and Properties*. Angewandte Chemie International Edition, 2015. **54**(14): p. 4160-4181 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201405310>.
- [11] Saburi, S., et al., *The refinement of the crystal structure of cuspidine*. Mineralogical Journal, 1977. **8**(5): p. 286-298 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2465/minerj.8.286>.
- [12] Cruz-Ramírez, A., et al., *An application of infrared analysis to determine the mineralogical phases formation in fluxes for thin slab casting of steel*. Journal of Fluorine Chemistry, 2011. **132**(5): p. 323-326 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluchem.2011.02.019>.
- [13] Coon, E., et al., *Viscosity and crystallization of bioactive glasses from 45S5 to 13-93*. International Journal of Applied Glass Science, 2021. **12**(1): p. 65-77 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijag.15837>.
- [14] Clupper, D.C. and L.L. Hench, *Crystallization kinetics of tape cast bioactive glass 45S5*. Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids, 2003. **318**(1): p. 43-48 DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093\(02\)01857-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3093(02)01857-4).
- [15] Zandi Karimi, A., E. Rezabeigi, and R.A.L. Drew, *Crystallization behavior of combeite in 45S5 Bioglass® via controlled heat treatment*. Journal of Non-Crystalline Solids, 2018. **502**: p. 176-183 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnoncrysol.2018.09.003>.
- [16] Golovchak, R., et al., *Influence of phase separation on the devitrification of 45S5 bioglass*. Acta Biomaterialia, 2014. **10**(11): p. 4878-4886 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.actbio.2014.07.024>.
- [17] Massera, J., et al., *Crystallization Mechanism of the Bioactive Glasses, 45S5 and S53P4*. Journal of the American Ceramic Society, 2012. **95**(2): p. 607-613 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1551-2916.2011.05012.x>.
- [18] Sung, Y.-M., *Nonisothermal phase formation kinetics in sol-gel-derived strontium bismuth tantalate*. Journal of Materials Research, 2001. **16**(7): p. 2039-2044 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1557/JMR.2001.0279>.
- [19] Kingery, W.D., H.K. Bowen, and D.R. Uhlmann, *Introduction to Ceramics*. 2 ed. 1976: Wiley. 1056 ISBN: 9780471478607.